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THIN-PLY EFFECTS ON LONG-TERM THERMAL STABILITY OF HIGH TEMPERATURE POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES

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OUTLINE

- Motivation
- Objective
- Materials
- Results
- Summary
- Acknowledgements

Overall objective

Develop and mature technologies associated with thermosetting polymer based high temperature carbon fibre composites so they can be used in future generation civil aircraft aero engines.

Goal of study

Investigate how the thin-ply effect can play a role for high temperature composites, where manufacturing induced residual stresses are very significant, and if this effect can provide positive influence on long-term thermal stability.

MATERIALS

Baseline laminates:

- Resin: NEXIMID® MHT-R
 - Thermosetting formulation for RTM
 - 6F-dianhydride (6-FDA) backbone
 - 4-(Phenylethynyl)Phthalic Anhydride (4-PEPA) end-group crosslinker
 - ethynyl bis-phthalic anhydride (EBPA) main chain cross-linker
 - T_g ~ 370°C
- Composites
 - [(-45/+45)/(90/0)]_{2s}
 - 370 g/m² 8-Harness Satin weave based on Cytec Thornel T650/35 (Sigmatex)
 - 3 mm thick
 - V_f 58%
 - CPT ~0.375 mm

Thin-ply laminates:

- Resin: NEXIMID® MHT-R
 - Thermosetting formulation for RTM
 - 6F-dianhydride (6-FDA) backbone
 - 4-(Phenylethynyl)Phthalic Anhydride (4-PEPA) end-group crosslinker
 - ethynyl bis-phthalic anhydride (EBPA) main chain cross-linker
 - T_g ~ 370°C
- Composites
 - [(-45/+45)/(90/0)]_{6s}
 - 82 g/m² spread-tow biaxial fabric based on IMS65 Toho Tenax fibres (Oxeon)
 - 2 mm thick
 - V_f 51%
 - CPT ~ 0,083 mm

Composite manufacturing

Stage	T [°C]	Time [min]	P [Bar]
Melt and homogenize	240	30	1
Degass under vacuum	240	10	<0.005
Inject resin in to mould	320	~ 5	≤12
Isothermal cure	320	60	12
Heating of tool	320 - 370	30	12
Isothermal cure	370	120	12
Cooling of tool	370 - 80	720	1
Demould	80		1

RTM-facilities for high temperature RTM at RISE SICOMP. Ability to process liquid resins with temperature up to 300°C.

Mechanical property knock-down at high temperatures and after ageing – *Baseline* materials

Tsampas, Fernberg, Joffe *J Comp Mat* 52 (2) 2018

Tsampas, Fernberg, Joffe *J Comp Mat* 52 (2) 20180

Potential motivation for thin-plies

Weight loss during ageing:

- Accelerating over time
- Influenced/governed by exposed surfaces
- Large experimental variability

Micro-defects present in actual heterogeneous microstructure could potentially explain variability

- Micro-cracks could serve as path for air/oxygen

Minimize occurrence of micro-cracks to reduce weight loss rate

Thin-ply composites to mitigate

- occurrence of manufacturing induced cracks
- thermal oxidative ageing

Real structures after manufacturing

Thin-ply composites to mitigate effects of high residual stresses

Linear elastic laminate theory

Assumption:

- $[-45/45/90/0]_{2S} \sim [(-45/45)/(90/0)]_{2S}$
- typical epoxy + carbon fibre ply properties
- 53 MPa transverse strength of UD-ply (database value)

Residual transverse thermal stress

- $\sigma_{22} \sim 75$ MPa after cooling by $\Delta T=300$ K

Results

Transverse cracking during tensile loading

- Quasi-static tensile loading – unloading test
 - Examine specimen edges for occurrence of cracks after each loading cycle
- **Very few or no cracks** after manufacturing
- **Cracking onset strain shifted** significantly
 - From about 0.3% to around 0.6%
- **Evidence of beneficial "thin-ply effect"**

Thermal oxidative stability – Weight loss @ 320°C

Sample dimensions:
75 mm x 11 mm x 2-3 mm

Thermal oxidative stability – weight loss relative to matrix weight @ 320°C

Sample dimensions:
80 mm x 11 mm x 2.2-3.2 mm

Thermal oxidative stability – weight loss relative to matrix weight @ 320°C

- Initial weight loss (1%) of moisture
- Similar accelerating trend as previous
- Large variations between batches
- Small variation within batches
- 5 – 8 % matrix mass loss after 500 h
 - Corresponding to 2-3 % composite sample weight loss
- **No noticeable improvement due to thin-plies**

Difference between two batches of *Baseline*

Satin weave batch 1

"voids and cracks present in micrograph"

Satin weave batch 2

"flawless micrograph"

Difference between two batches of *Baseline*

Thin-ply composites

"micrograph indicating some micro-pores"

Satin weave batch 2

"flawless micrograph"

Difference between two batches of Baseline

Thin-ply composites

"micrograph indicating some micro-pores"

Thin-ply composites

Summary and conclusions

- Thin-ply composites samples based on 82 g/m² spread-tow biaxial carbon fibre fabric and high temperature polyimide were successfully manufactured
- A clear thin-ply effect was observed in terms of
 - Almost no manufacturing induced transverse crack for thin-ply composites
 - Onset of transverse cracking in tensile tests was shifted towards higher strains (from 0.3 % (*Baseline*) to 0.6 % (*Thin-ply*))
- No detectable positive thin-ply effect with respect to thermal oxidative ageing
 - Difference in mass degradation rate appears to be dominated by presence of defects
 - Difference in void content and cracks between two different *Baseline* batches
 - Presence of what appears as micro-defects between individual fibres in *Thin-ply* laminates
- Mechanisms governing difference in degradation rate remains to verify and deserves more research
 - Influence of fibres (stiffness, sizing), interfaces
 - Stress relaxation and/or build up, evolution of matrix properties over time, etc...

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